

Determination of Neuro-Muscular, Circulatory, Pulmonary Function and Psychological Fitness among the Second Year Indian Students

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Short Review

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Determination of Neuro-Muscular, Circulatory, Pulmonary Function and Psychological Fitness among the Second Year Indian Students

Saptarshi Pal and Shavkin Vladimir

Scientific advisor- Associate Professor, Department of Normal Physiology, Russia

***Corresponding Author:** Saptarshi Pal, Shavkin Vladimir, Scientific advisor- Associate Professor, Department of Normal Physiology, Head - Professor KYZNETCHOV V, Acad. E.A. WAGNER Perm State Medical University, Perm, Russia

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Abstract

The Principal aimed to reevaluate and detect the methods hand grip strength, pulse, arterial pressure, lung function and psychological fitness between male and female. The observation was based on some groups of Indian students of Perm State Medical University and finding the average values between these tests.

Keywords: Maximum strength; Average Vital capacity; Arterial pressure

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